

SICOT

44th SICOT Orthopaedic World Congress
25-27 September 2024
BELGRADE, SERBIA

Combined meeting with the Serbian Orthopaedic Trauma Association

ABSTRACT BOOK

Free Papers

Application of Bone Marrow Aspirate Concentrate, Cancellous Bone Autograft, Platelet Rich Plasma, and Autologous Fibrin for Femur Non-unions: A Case Series

Oliver Dulic¹, Dzihan Abazovic³, Gordan Gavrilovic⁴, Predrag Rasovic¹, Ivica Lalic², Srdjan Ninkovic¹, Mirko Obradovic¹, Mile Bjelobrk¹, Milan Tosic¹, Branko Bjelobrk¹, Milan Milinkov¹

¹University Of Novi Sad, Serbia, Medical Faculty, university Clinical Center Of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia, ²University Bussines Academy Novi Sad, Faculty for Pharmacy, Novi Sad, Serbia, ³Renova Hospital, Belgrade, Serbia, ⁴Atlas Hospital, Belgrade, Serbia

SOTA New Technologies & Regenerative Medicine Free Papers, MR 7, September 25, 2024, 10:15 - 12:00

Aim: This study aimed to assess the efficacy of a novel bioregenerative scaffold comprising bone marrow aspirate, cancellous bone autograft, platelet-rich plasma, and autologous fibrin in the treatment of supracondylar femur non-unions.

Methods & Materials: Four patients with non-unions following multiple unsuccessful surgical interventions underwent bone stabilization surgery along with the application of the innovative bioregenerative scaffold. Evaluation of outcomes was conducted through preoperative and postoperative assessments at 6, 12, and 24 months, utilizing X-rays for radiological confirmation and subjective assessment scales to gauge functional improvements.

Results: Radiographic analysis demonstrated successful healing of all non-unions with adequate callus formation evident within the specified timeframe. Notably, within 6 months post-surgery, all patients achieved the milestone of full weight-bearing walking without experiencing pain or discomfort. Statistical analysis revealed highly significant improvements across all subjective assessment scales compared to baseline values, indicating robust functional recovery and symptom relief.

Conclusions: This study underscores the potential of the novel bioregenerative scaffold as a promising therapeutic option for managing supracondylar femur non-unions refractory to conventional treatments. The observed successful outcomes, including prompt healing and restoration of functional abilities, highlight the clinical efficacy and potential utility of this approach in addressing challenging cases of non-union following multiple surgical failures. Further investigation and validation in larger cohorts are warranted to establish its broader applicability and long-term efficacy.

Keywords: femur non-union, bone marrow aspirate, platelet rich plasma, autologous bone graft, autologous fibrin, regenerative orthopedics